

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE STRUCTURE RELEVANT TO LAMINATE DESIGN GUIDELINES

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1 Introduction

Composite materials, especially carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) with continuous carbon fibers, are widely used in the Aerospace industry. Thanks to their unique specific properties, CFRPs allow realizing lightweight structures with high mechanical performance. However, the potential of these materials remains rarely employed to its full extent while designing customized materials that are locally matching the spatial distribution of the stresses within a whole structure. Laminates can be tailored by optimizing its lay-up and number of plies. Thickness variations are obtained by locally adding or dropping plies in the structure. The developments realized during the last decade about composite optimization methods enable to optimize both stacking sequences and thickness variations [1]. However those methods do not account for many industrial design guidelines, particularly those related to thickness variations (e.g., ply drops). In this context, this study demonstrates the feasibility of a combined lay-up and thickness optimization in the case of a satellite part, while respecting the design guidelines and the manufacturing constraints that are specific to laminate composite structures.

In this study, an original optimization method, specific to composite laminates, has been developed and is presented in the related paper [2]. Here, the method is applied for a real structure intended to Space application. Section 2 of this article briefly presents the specifications of the structure, its design constraints, as well as the modeling work. Section 3 reminds the main features of the optimization method. The results are discussed in the last section. It is shown that it is possible to

increase the stiffness and reduce the total mass simultaneously. Significant performance gains are observed when new designs are compared to the reference one provided by classical design approach without optimization. A brief comparison of the possible gains for a laminate of 2D-woven fabrics and a laminate of UD prepreg plies is presented to identify the best technological solution.

2 The optimal design problem

2.1 Satellite antenna mounting bracket

The composite part presented in this paper is a satellite antenna mounting bracket, as shown in **Fig.1**. The bracket provides the mechanical connection between the satellite structure and the mounting stand of a telecom antenna, both made of CFRP materials. The bracket is also expected to minimize the differential thermal expansion due to large temperature changes throughout the satellite's orbit. Initially made of titanium alloy, the bracket needs a new design intended for the use of composite materials with respect to the following specifications:

- *Stiffness*, through its first natural frequency in order to keep the antenna aligned with its target.
- *Strength*. Resistance to a given critical load case in order to ensure full functionality when mechanical stresses peak.
- *Mass*. Overall net mass of the composite bracket must not exceed the mass of the titanium alloy one.

In this context, the company MECANO I&D, in collaboration with ONERA, developed a new solution, as shown in **Fig.2**, by replacing the original material by a CFRP made through 'resin transfer molding' (RTM) of a preform of 2D-woven

fabrics. This new solution resulted in reducing the mass by 35%. This result was achieved without numerical optimization. Prototypes of the new bracket have been built and tested to validate the concept and its performance, with satisfactory results. The purpose of this work is to explore the opportunities for improvement provided by the parametric optimization of the bracket.

2.2 Formulation of the optimization problem

The multiobjective optimization problem of a laminate generally consists in finding the possible trade-offs between two or more objectives while manipulating variables, such as the number of plies, their order and their orientations. This differentiates it from the feasibility problem solved before the design step. A constrained multicriteria optimization problem can be formulated from the specifications detailed in section 2.1. The objectives are to maximize the first natural frequency and minimize the total mass of the bracket. The optimization variables are the stacking sequences, the order of the inserted plies, and the number of plies per zone. These zones represent distinct regions of the bracket where its thickness and material properties do not vary. Each zone may be directly identified from the geometry of the composite structure. Constraints are divided into two categories. The first one gathers analysis constraints, that are most likely mechanical quantities to compute, and often as costly as evaluations of the objectives. In the case of this study, a simple failure criterion is required. The second category gathers design constraints; here design guidelines; which intervenes essentially while generating a solution, with relatively low costs. These allow introducing notions of composite know-how in the optimization process to get closer to the reality of the design problem, but also integrating manufacturing constraints while solving the problem. All these constraints contribute to result in feasible composite solutions.

2.3 Laminate design guidelines

The laminate design guidelines, created from known manufacturing issues and feedbacks in the industry [3,4,5], make a representative set of industrial constraints for composite structure pre-design.

The laminate design guidelines, particularly restrictive on the combinations and permutations about stacking sequence variables, may be summarized as follows:

- Symmetry of the sequence about the mid-plane. This guideline aims at eliminating the couplings between membrane and bending behavior, and avoiding residual strains that may result within the laminate.
- Balance of the sequence between $+\theta^\circ$ and $-\theta^\circ$ plies. This guideline aims at eliminating the in-plane couplings between shear and traction.
- Contiguity, i.e. no more than two plies with the same orientation should be stacked together. This guideline aims at reducing the damage phenomena sensitive to the thickness of the layers, such as free edges effects or matrix cracking.
- Disorientation limited to 45° between two plies. This rule minimizes the effects of interlaminar shear, and limits the problems of delamination at free edges.
- A proportion of 10% for each 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° oriented plies. This guideline prevents that the behavior of the matrix becomes dominant on the overall behavior of the laminate in some directions, and minimizes the Poisson ration of the whole laminate.
- Damage tolerance improvement through $\pm 45^\circ$ -oriented surface plies protecting the most stressed plies whose orientations are closer to the main loading direction. This guideline aims at limiting the consequences of any surface damage and possible scratches.

Thickness variations along the structure are ensured by tapering the laminate through ply drop-off as illustrated in **Fig.3**. Dropping a ply off may locally weaken the structure through delamination. So sequencing the ply drops is a task to achieve with caution, considering six ply-drop design guidelines intended for aerospace structures:

- Covering the laminate with continuous surface plies,
- Taper angle smoothed to 7° , i.e. a minimal stagger distance about eight times the total thickness of all the plies dropped,
- Dropping off a maximum of two plies at the same time,
- Adjacent ply drops limited to three,

- Ply drops alternatively far from and close to the mid-plane,
 - Laminate design guidelines to extend to tapers.
- These guidelines also make the structure more resistant to micro-buckling and improve their manufacturability.

In addition to these local guidelines, two more global rules exist, specific to taper composites:

- Continuity, i.e. all the plies from the thinner panel are expected to be kept within the structure to ensure structural continuity.
- Δn -rule, i.e. the number ply drops is limited between distinct zones to minimize stress concentrations.

2.4 Model and parameters

The pre-design FE model consists in a shell model of the composite part mid-layer. The model is developed with ABAQUS as shown in **Fig.4**. The mesh is composed of reduced integration quadrangular shell elements. Thicknesses and composite lay-ups can be assigned to each element or element set. As a consequence, stacking sequences are parameterized within the model without modifying the mesh. Thus, the parameterization of the model only consists in composite lay-up definition associated with a set of elements.

The connection from the bracket to the satellite is modeled through blocking all the degrees of freedom of the nodes of the edges of the holes on side #1. For each hole of side #2, the nodes of the circumference are connected through rigid links to a reference point located at the center of the hole. All the three reference points, corresponding to the three holes on side #2, are connected to a fourth one located at their isobarycenter. The efforts are inserted at this reference point.

Two different analyzes are performed for each evaluation of a solution. A linear elastic static analysis is done in order to evaluate the resistance of the structure to a critical load case indicated in the specifications. A fragile failure criterion results from the post-treatment of the previous calculation. Here, a Tsai-Hill failure criterion is used. The first natural frequency is calculated from a modal analysis with small perturbations performed with

the unloaded structure. The mass is estimated through the densities of the materials and the volume calculation tools provided by the software.

The reference bracket suggested by MECANO I&D is realized from cut plies depending on different perimeters of pattern with variable complexity. These plies are successively formed through folding on male or female molding dies and stacked as two dry performs, slightly powdered, to be assembled when the RTM mold is closed. In order to transcribe the reality of this process in the model, it is necessary to take into account the shapes of the patterns and the folding inclinations realized to define the local orientations of the material within each zone of the structure. Indeed, the angle between sides #1 and #3 (or #4) is an acute angle whereas sides #2 and #3 (or #4) trace an obtuse angle. These angles imply a redirection of the orthotropy axes (1,2,3) of the material in accordance with the projection of the global coordinates (x,y,z) on the sides of the bracket. This redirection evolves within the fillets' radii between two sides, as illustrated in **Fig.5**.

3 Optimization of the stacking sequences and tapering through ply-drop off

3.1 Ply-drop management through stacking sequence tables

The local variations of stiffness in laminated structures are obtained through ply drops. The design guidelines listed in section 2.3 entail that the whole stack of the thinnest zone of the structure runs uninterruptedly through the others. Moreover, in order to ensure the structural integrity of the part, it is forbidden to cut a ply to change the fiber direction. Such issue is known in the literature as *laminar blending*. The notion of laminar blending has been introduced for the first time in [6]. Different strategies to solve this problem have been suggested in the literature [1,2]. The most successful method is currently the *guide-based blending* presented in [7]. This method consists in defining all the stacking sequences of the structure from the thickest one only, also known as *guiding stack*. All the thinner laminates are defined by deleting contiguous stacks of plies from the guide laminate, starting from the surface of the guide stack ('outer blending'), or from its mid-layer

(‘inner blending’), as illustrated in **Fig.6**. Hence, guide-based blending allows ensuring perfectly the continuity of the plies between the different zones of the structure, without adding any constraints to the optimization problem and adding only one variable per zone (the number of dropped plies). However, the choice to drop groups of contiguous plies substantially restricts the search space, so that it is impossible to optimize the order of the ply drops through the thickness of the laminate. It is therefore impossible to comply with the taper design guidelines.

In order to overcome such limitation and represent the evolution of the lay-up within the structure, Stacking Sequence Tables (SST) are introduced in this study. SSTs are used in aeronautic industry for composite panels manufacturing. They are most commonly created by experts, but here an original use of the SSTs is presented to generalize guide-based blending and allow the optimization of the order and location of the ply drops within the structure. The SST helps monitoring the succession of the ply drops ensuring the transition between a thick stack with N_{max} plies and a thin stack with N_{min} plies. The ply drops are defined one by one. Read from the left to the right, the SST describes a thickness diminution, and conversely. Knowing the distribution of the number of plies in a structure, varying in the range $[N_{min}, N_{max}]$, the SST defines all the laminates of the structure, in the constant thickness zones as well as in the taper since each ply drop is described individually. The SST does not take into account any particular stagger distance. These are most likely represented in the model when they are required. Using the SSTs allows defining solutions that respect the design guidelines. An example of such SST is shown in **Fig.7**. In this study, symmetrical guiding stacks are used exclusively. Taking advantage of the symmetry, only the half of the SST is represented in the following, as illustrated in **Fig.8**. Since SST describes a blending process in a range of thicknesses, it can be shared by several solutions as long as they belong to this range. Indeed, the structure is fully represented only if its thickness distribution is featured in the solution.

3.2 Specialization of an EA to the joint optimization of stacking sequence tables and thickness distributions.

The method intended to solve the optimization problem is built from a Pareto-based multiobjective EA [8]. Its operating principle is sketched in **Fig.9**. In this study, a specialized version of this algorithm is developed for SST optimization [2] and applied to the antenna mounting bracket described earlier.

Specific operators have been developed so that the generated solutions satisfy the design guidelines each time the algorithm iterates. For this purpose, a specific encoding is used for the SST. The symmetry of the guiding stack allows representing only the half of the SST and therefore reduces the encoding of the solutions. This encoding, illustrated in **Fig.10**, consists in three chromosomes, each corresponding to a set of optimization variables:

- Chromosome N_{str} represents the thickness distribution, as total number of plies, within the structure and consists of as many genes as there are effective zones in the structure.
- Chromosome SST_{lam} represents the sequence of the guiding stack for generating the SST and consists of $N_{max}/2$ genes.
- Chromosome SST_{ins} represents the ranks of the plies to be introduced to form the SST. The insertion order is given here by numbers in ascending order. The plies of the thin stack cover the entire SST. This chromosome has the same size than SST_{lam} and contains $N_{min}/2$ zeros, corresponding to plies covering the whole structure.

4 Results

The objectives of the optimization problem presented in this paper are to maximize the stiffness of the antenna bracket through its first natural frequency and to minimize its mass. The MECANO I&D’s bracket is made of G803/RTM6, a balanced orthotropic 2D woven fabric, whose fibers are T300. Thus the problem is solved for G803/RTM6 then T300/914, a unidirectional prepreg ply with transverse isotropy, to explore the possibilities that UD offers compared to 2D material. Properties of G803/RTM6 presented in **Tab.1** are expressed in the orthotropy axes of the ply for a fiber volume fraction of 56%. Its in-plane properties have been

experimentally characterized by MECANO I&D. Through-the-thickness properties E_3 , ν_{23} and ν_{31} are assumed to be close to the transversal properties of the unidirectional prepreg ply T300/914. Failure properties, of the G803/RTM6 ply and the T300/914 ply are given in **Tab.2**. Ply thickness is about 0.28 mm for the G803/RTM6 and 0.158 mm for the T300/914. The thickness, or number of plies in each zone, is limited by at least 12 plies up to 34 plies in the case of the optimization with G803/RTM6, and at least 18 plies up to 68 plies for T300/914. Ply orientations are limited to the following set of admissible values $\{0^\circ, \pm 15^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 60^\circ, \pm 75^\circ \text{ and } 90^\circ\}$.

The evolutionary algorithm is set to run six thousand solution evaluations during the whole optimization process, as outlined in **Tab.3**. These are represented in the objectives space in **Fig.11** and **Fig.12**, including optimal solutions for both materials as red diamonds. Regarding the optimization performed with 2D-woven fabrics, **Fig.11** shows that the algorithm converges to solutions included in the bottom right quadrant, where the solutions improve the reference solution towards the two objectives. By repeating the exercise with the UD prepreg, a significant gain in stiffness for an equivalent mass is achieved, as shown in **Fig.13**. Such increase can be explained by the higher stiffness in the fiber direction of the T300/914. In addition, the optimization problem has more degrees of freedom by using UD plies. Indeed, these are thinner and therefore more numerous than 2D plies through the thickness of the laminate. While increasing the number of plies, SSTs are enlarged, as well as the number of possible combinations and permutations of the optimization variables. The lightest G803/RTM6 solution, whose SST is detailed in **Fig.14** and the properties listed in **Tab.4**, allows weight savings of 10% compared to the reference solution. The lightest T300/914 solution performs 12%-weight savings compared to the reference solution.

In the optimized design, it can be seen that the tapers are located within the fillet radii connecting the faces of the bracket. Moreover, ply drops are distributed over a very short distance. The representation of fillet radii is therefore restricted in the pre-design model. However, the results of the

pre-design model are relatively satisfactory considering the reference solution manufactured and tested by MECANO I&D, so that the model is considered to give fair trends over the design space. In addition, the guidelines aiming at limiting the risks of premature failure are used in this model to overcome the inherent limitations of pre-design in predicting the behavior and failure of the structure, unlike detailed analysis. Since most of the design guidelines have been thought for large structures, this may call into question their relevance with this application. They are probably pushed beyond their range of validity in this study. For relevance, performing a numerical validation based on a detailed three-dimensional model, and eventually conducting an experimental validation are expected as future works.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents the application of an optimization method, dedicated to variable-thickness laminated composite structures, to a demonstration case provided by MECANO I&D. The method applied here has been developed in the context of this study and described in the related paper [2]. The demonstration case consists of a mounting bracket designed to connect a satellite antenna to a satellite structure. The optimization problem is formulated based on the specifications of the structure. A pre-design FE model of the bracket is created in order to represent the complexity of the structure without involving too many details and excessive computation costs. The problem takes into account the guidelines related to laminate composite structures. To enforce these guidelines and ensure the structural continuity of the design, stacking sequence tables are used. The problem is solved using a multiobjective evolutionary algorithm. A specific encoding of the solutions is used that represents the stacking sequences, the order of the ply insertions within the constitutive laminates of the structure and the thickness distribution over the whole structure. The optimization problem is solved first for a base ply made of a carbon/epoxy 2D-woven fabric, then using a carbon/epoxy UD ply. This allows exploring two different design spaces and achieving optimal solutions which improve significantly the reference solution. ONERA and MECANO I&D

are currently working together to test the method on new designs of the antenna mounting bracket and then validate it through the completion of a demonstration prototype for experimental validation.

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Fig.1. Design of the titanium alloy solution of the satellite antenna mounting bracket.

Fig.2. Photographs of the CFRP solution made by MECANO I&D (front and rear views).

Fig.3. Taper section with four inner ply-drops.

Fig.4. Thickness-rendered view of the reference G803/RTM6 satellite antenna mounting bracket.

Fig.5. View of the model of the mid-layer of the bracket with redirection of the orthotropy axes.

Fig.6. Guide-based blending definitions [7].

Ply No.	Number of plies					Inserted plies
	16	15	14	13	12	
1	45	45	45	45	45	
2	90	90	90	90	90	
3	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	
4	0					←
5	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	
6	0	0	0	0	0	
7	45	45	45	45	45	
8	90	90	90	90	90	←
9	90	90	90	90		←
10	45	45	45	45	45	
11	0	0	0	0	0	
12	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	
13	0	0				←
14	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	
15	90	90	90	90	90	
16	45	45	45	45	45	

Guide stack : [45/90/-45/0/-45/0/45/90]s
 Thinnest stack : [45/90/-45/-45/0/45]s

Fig.7. Representation of a blending process through SST, from a guide laminate to a thin laminate.

Fig.8. Condensed view of the SST in Fig.7.

Fig.9. Flow chart of the evolutionary algorithm.

N_{str}	14	12	14	16				
SST_{lam}	45	90	-45	0	-45	0	45	90
SST_{ins}	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1

Fig.10. Encoding of the solution in Fig.8.

Materials	G803/RTM6	T300/914
E_1 (GPa)	61,23	140
E_2 (GPa)	61,23	10
E_3 (GPa)	10,00	-
ν_{12}	0,03	0,31
ν_{23}	0,30	-
ν_{31}	0,30	-
G_{12} (GPa)	3,46	4,40
G_{23} (GPa)	2,96	-
G_{31} (GPa)	2,96	-
μ (kg/m ³)	1496	1760

Tab.1. Elastic properties of G803/RTM6 and T300/914 plies.

Materials	G803/RTM6	T300/914
X_t (MPa)	700	1500
Y_t (MPa)	690	27
X_c (MPa)	-468	-900
Y_c (MPa)	-438	-200
S (MPa)	103	80

Tab.2. Failure properties of G803/RTM6 and T300/914 plies.

Crossing	0.3
Mutation	0.9
Initial population	60
Current population	30
Archive population	60
Generations	200

Tab.3. Algorithm settings.

Fig.11. Solutions in the objectives space for G803/RTM6 woven fabric.

Fig.12. Solutions in the objectives space for T300/914 unidirectional plies.

Fig.13. Comparison of optimal solutions.

	Ref.	G803/RTM6	T300/914
Thickness distribution (mm)	9,24	8,40	8,22
	5,32	3,36	3,48
	3,36	3,36	2,84
Thickness distribution (No. plies)			
Zone 1	33	30	52
Zone 2	19	12	22
Zone 3	12	12	18
Total mass (g)	154.314	139.500	135.520
1 st natural frequency (Hz)	879	905	880
Failure criterion max. value	0.751	0.992	0.997

Tab.4. Characteristics of the lightest solution within the Pareto front for each material.

	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12
1	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
2	0	0	0	0	0							
3	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
4	-15	-15	-15	-15	-15	-15	-15	-15	-15			
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	-45	-45	-45	-45								
7	-30	-30										
8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	45	45	45									
10	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15				
11	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30		
12	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45
13	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75					
14	75	75	75	75	75	75						
15	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75	-75
16	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
17	30											

Encoding : [30|12|12]
 [45/0/30/-15/0/-45/-30/0/45/15/-30/-45/-75/75/-75/75/30]s
 [0|7|1|3|0|8|10|0|9|4|2|0|5|6|0|11]

Fig.14. Stacking sequence of an optimal G803/RTM6 solution.